

BREADCRUMB

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DELIVERABLE D5.7

Practice Abstracts - Batch 1

BREADCRUMB

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Coordinator	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK - EV ILVO		
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D5. 7 - PRACTICE ABSTRACTS- BATCH 1

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CA	Consortium Agreement
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CS	Case Study
EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EU	European Union
FC	Food Chain
FLW	Food Loss & Waste
FMS	Food Marketing Standards
FW	Food Waste
GA	Grant Agreement
HE	Horizon Europe
M	Month
PA	Practice Abstract
PC	Project Coordinator
R&I	Research & Innovation
RIA	Research and Innovation Action

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The BREADCRUMB project, funded under the Horizon Europe programme, tackles the growing challenge of food waste (FW) linked to Food Marketing Standards (FMS) across Europe. These standards set by both public authorities and private entities aim to ensure quality, safety, and consistency in agricultural products. However, they often result in rigid requirements that can cause significant amounts of edible food to be discarded due to cosmetic imperfections or minor specification deviations.

As part of its mission to bridge research and practice, BREADCRUMB contributes to the EU CAP Network and EIP-AGRI platforms through the creation of Practice Abstracts (PAs). These abstracts present new, practitioner-friendly knowledge in a concise and actionable format for farmers, advisors, and rural stakeholders. Deliverable D5.7 compiles the first two of four planned PAs, developed under Work Package 5: Research and Innovation Scale-up.

Practice Abstract 1, led by VLTN, introduces the Inventory of Food Marketing Standards, a curated database of public and private FMS across six food categories (fruits, vegetables, meat, eggs, cereals, and fish). This tool is designed to help producers and businesses navigate the often-overlapping and complex regulatory environment. It will also serve as a basis for identifying where FMS may be adjusted to enable the marketing of suboptimal but safe products that currently risk being wasted.

Practice Abstract 2, developed by ILVO, focuses on the impact of strict FMS on food waste across multiple commodities. It highlights specific examples such as misshapen fruits, discoloured vegetables, or eggs with non-uniform shells that are discarded due to not meeting visual or weight specifications. The abstract proposes actionable strategies to mitigate FW, including promoting societal acceptance of imperfect produce and strengthening collaboration along the food supply chain.

Together, these abstracts contribute to the EU CAP Network and EIP-AGRI platforms, which aim to disseminate innovation broadly across EU agriculture and rural development. These abstracts aim to enhance the visibility and real-world applicability of BREADCRUMB's research findings, promoting a more flexible and sustainable food system.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BREADCRUMB Project Overview

The BREADCRUMB project aims to provide an empirical evidence-based understanding of the purpose and nature of Food Marketing Standards (FMS), their impact on Food Waste (FW) generation, and based on this evidence, propose interventions that strike a balance between reducing FW and the other objectives pursued by these standards. Furthermore, the project strives to improve market access for suboptimal foods by guiding food businesses to select appropriate marketing channels, and by fostering change in consumers' acceptance of suboptimal foods. All of this information will be structured into operational and policy guidance on how to prevent / reduce FW related to marketing standards.

More specifically, the Grant Agreement (GA) defines the following **procedure for the project** (Figure 1): "(i) establish a holistic view of marketing standards and identify those with key relevance to FW generation; (ii) create evidence-based estimates of FW generated as a consequence of marketing standards; (iii) provide solutions that alleviate the negative impacts of marketing standards on FW, based on a valid understanding of the underlying mechanisms of FW generation and trade-offs with other objectives (re-balancing marketing standards); (iv) enhance the business potential of "suboptimal" foods; (v) inform and guide food businesses, consumers, owners of standards and policy regulators on how to prevent/reduce FW related to marketing standards".¹

Figure 1: The BREADCRUMB project at a glance

Source: BREADCRUMB Grant Agreement, Part B, page 101 (electronic version).

¹ European Commission. (2023). "Grant Agreement Project BREADCRUMB." European Commission, European Research Executive Agency, (November), page 101 (electronic version).

Moreover, the project intends to incorporate a gender perspective and intersectional analysis across the project. Both are pertinent to better understand the design and response to marketing standards affecting food choices, usage, and waste.

To verify the results, the project will employ various **validation** methods involving participants external to the project. These include:

- ✓ The External Advisory Board (EAB, 6 individuals: researchers, practitioners with complementary expertise);
- ✓ Food Marketing Standards Interest Group (FMSIG, 25 individuals: food businesses, civil society organisations, FW entrepreneurs, policy actors, and Joint Research Centre (JRC) representatives);
- ✓ Specified consultation events, such as workshops, to widen the validation process with a larger group of diverse actors.

The research methodology and approach within the project has been approved by the COMESH **ethical committee** of the project's coordinator institution.

1.2 Aim and structure of the report

This document is developed in the framework of the Work Package 5: Research and Innovation scale-up. The main objective of the Deliverable 5.7 is to report the first 2 Practice Abstracts (first batch) of the project undertaken during the second year of the project.

A total target number of 4 practice abstracts (PA) is foreseen for the project reported in D5.7 and D5.8. This first deliverable, D5.7, presents the first batch of practice abstracts (based on work done in WP1 and WP2), submitted by M18 of project execution (June 2025). Deliverable D5.8, due in M36, presents the second batch of practice abstract (based on work done in WP3 and WP4). This report is organised into five main sections followed by a conclusion.

1. **Introduction:** Provides an overview of the objectives of the BREADCRUMB project.
2. **Context and background:** Outlines the background of the EU CAP Network and EIP-AGRI. It also introduces the concept of the practice abstract.
3. **EIP-AGRI HE common format online template:** Describes the structure of the EIP-AGRI HE online format, including its required project information and submission requirements for practice abstracts.
4. **Submitted Practice Abstracts:** Presents the two practice abstracts from the first batch: PA 1 (prepared by VLTN) and PA 2 (prepared by ILVO, the BREADCRUMB coordinator).
5. **Key conclusions:** key insights are summarised.

2 CONTEXT OF THE EU CAP NETWORK AND THE EIP-AGRI

The resulting innovative knowledge from this project will feed into the **EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Network** and the **EIP-AGRI (European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability)** website for broad dissemination to practitioners. End-user material will be produced in the form of a number of summaries for practitioners in the EIP-AGRI common format ("practice abstracts"). The project details will also be submitted to the EU CAP Network platform.

The EU CAP Network and EIP-AGRI are closely linked, as EIP-AGRI is an integral part of the EU CAP Network.

- The EU CAP Network was established to support the implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), bringing together different stakeholders involved in rural development, agricultural innovation, and environmental sustainability. It serves as an umbrella network, integrating multiple initiatives, including EIP-AGRI.
- EIP-AGRI operates within this framework to foster innovation in agriculture, forestry, and rural areas, promoting cooperation between farmers, researchers, advisors, and agribusinesses to accelerate the uptake of innovative practices.

Thus, **EIP-AGRI is a key component of the EU CAP Network, focused specifically on innovation and knowledge exchange.**

EU-funded projects play a pivotal role in both the EU CAP Network and EIP-AGRI by generating knowledge and innovation, facilitating multi-actor collaboration, providing insights to shape CAP policies, and ensuring real-world application of results. Being part of these networks offers numerous benefits, including increased visibility, enhanced dissemination greater impact valuable networking opportunities with key stakeholders. Additionally, it enables knowledge exchange with other initiatives, fostering synergies and best practice sharing.

2.1 Practice abstracts

Practice abstracts are concise, structured summaries designed to present new knowledge or innovative solutions generated by the EU-funded projects, accessible and applicable to practitioners.

Required for multi-actor Horizon Europe projects, they facilitate knowledge transfer to farmers, advisors, and rural stakeholders by presenting project outcomes in a clear and practical format, free from technical jargon, making the information accessible to non-academic audiences.

These abstracts should clearly state the problem addressed, the innovative solution, and expected benefits. They play a critical role in translating research findings into actionable insights, ensuring that

innovations reach end-users in agriculture and forestry rather than remaining confined to academic or policy discussions. By bridging research and practice, they make technical information more digestible and widely available, especially to those without direct access to scientific publications.

Moreover, the Practice Abstracts contribute directly to the objectives of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) by facilitating the uptake of innovation within the agricultural sector. They serve as a tool to support policy implementation by providing clear, concise, and practical guidance on how new solutions can be integrated into farming practices. This, in turn, encourages the real-world application of research outputs, ensuring that innovations developed within EU-funded projects do not remain confined to theoretical discussions but are adopted in practice.

Beyond supporting CAP objectives and encouraging the uptake of innovations, Practice Abstracts bring several benefits. They enhance the impact and exploitation of project results by ensuring their effective use by stakeholders. Additionally, for multi-actor projects, they are a mandatory requirement under EU funding regulations, reinforcing compliance with dissemination and exploitation obligations.

By simplifying complex research findings, these abstracts strengthen stakeholder engagement, facilitating the adoption of new knowledge by farmers, policymakers, and advisors. Their structured approach also contributes to long-term project visibility and legacy, ensuring that innovations remain relevant and accessible beyond the project's duration. In this way, they increase the likelihood of research outcomes being recognized, referenced, and implemented across the agricultural sector.

3 EIP-AGRI COMMON FORMAT FOR PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

To contribute to the EU project database within the EU CAP Network and facilitate effective knowledge sharing, the BREADCRUMB project must complete the EIP-AGRI common format table (see Figure 2), which includes a project profile and practice abstract(s). This structured template standardizes the submission of project information, providing clear guidance on formatting, required fields, and submission procedures. The primary objective of the EIP-AGRI common format is to disseminate project results in a concise and accessible manner.

Prior to submitting the first set of Practice Abstracts for BREADCRUMB, the project communication partner (PNO) registered the initiative on the EU CAP Network website.

3.1 Guideline and templates of EIP-AGRI common format for Horizon Europe projects

The EIP-AGRI common format template provides a standardized framework for presenting project data across EIP-AGRI and CAP-related initiatives, ensuring consistency and clarity in information sharing. Designed with a structured approach, the template is divided into multiple sections, each containing specific fields that need to be completed. To help users prioritize their inputs, these elements are categorized as obligatory, recommended, or optional, allowing for flexibility while maintaining the essential details required for effective knowledge dissemination. The content of the common format can be updated at any moment of the project life-cycle when useful.

The template of the EIP-AGRI common format for Horizon Europe (HE) projects (illustrated on Figure 2) is available in an online format once registering the project on the [EU CAP Network website](#).

Figure 2. EIP-AGRI Horizon Europe 2023-2027 online format

3.1.1 Required project information

The following fields are mandatory and must be completed in the prescribed order. This section ensures that all essential project details are captured for transparency and compliance.

- ✓ **Project information:** includes the Editor (The person responsible for compiling the project information), the official project title, project acronym and Grant Agreement ID.
- ✓ **Project Period:** Start and end dates of the project, type of Horizon project and budget information.
- ✓ **Description of the activities:** Details the project activities, contribution to CAP-specific objectives and EU strategies, as well as Keyword-Category for easier classification indexing.
- ✓ **Geographical information:** Specifies where the main activities of the project take place.
- ✓ **Project Coordinator and partners:** Identifies the entity or person managing the project and lists all organizations involved in the project.

- ✓ **Additional information about the project:** provides further details such as project email.

3.1.2 Structure of the template

The template includes multiple sections covering different aspects of the project. This structure helps organize project information systematically for efficient review and dissemination.

- ✓ **Project Information:** Main details of the project.
- ✓ **Geographical information:** location of project activities
- ✓ **Keywords:** Thematic classification for indexing and searchability.
- ✓ **Coordinator and partners:** Organizations involved in the project.
- ✓ **Audiovisual Materials & Websites:** Links to videos, reports, and websites for dissemination.
- ✓ **Practice Abstracts:** Summarized outputs designed for practical implementation.

3.1.3 Submission requirements

All required fields must be filled before submission. This section outlines the standards and formatting rules to ensure consistency and compliance with EU guidelines.

- ✓ The information must align with the official CAP Strategic Plan and EIP-AGRI requirements.
- ✓ The Practice Abstract should be formatted according to the predefined Excel structure to facilitate processing and review:
 - Length: 255 characters limit (excluding spaces) for the title section and maximum 2000 characters (excluding spaces) for the findings.
 - Font: Arial or Calibri in size 11.
 - Language: English
 - Additional dissemination and exploitation material(s): additional materials which are useful and attractive for practitioners (e.g., link to relevant websites, social media, videos, pictures, pdf files, other dissemination materials).
- ✓ The final abstracts must be submitted in the official EU CAP Network website, ensuring compliance with EU CAP Network dissemination guidelines.
- ✓ The content must be practitioner-friendly, making it accessible to farmers, advisors, and policymakers

3.1.4 Registration of the BREADCRUMB project at the EU CAP Network website

The project was registered on the [EU CAP Network website](#) in order to upload the PAs in the online format form. The second step after the registration was waiting for a review and a confirmation by the EU CAP Network that the PAs were successfully submitted, as shown on Figure 3, The submitted PAs of BREADCRUMB can be found at this [link](#).

PROJECT - RESEARCH AND INNOVATION
Bringing Evidence-based food Chain solutions to prevent and RedUce food waste related to Marketing standards, and deliver climate and circularity co-Benefits

Innovation, Knowledge exchange & EIP-AGRI
 ONGOING | 2024 - 2026
 Belgium, Spain, Italy, Denmark, Germany, Portugal, Slovenia

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Overview Practice Abstracts Contacts

Context

BREADCRUMB will generate an inventory of both public and private food marketing standards and provide empirical evidence on FW levels associated with these regulations across five key food commodities: fruits & vegetables, meat, eggs, cereals, and fish. By employing advanced modeling techniques, the project will assess the underlying mechanisms that drive food waste, offering insights into how standards can be adjusted without compromising their original objectives.

The project also integrates behavioral and economic research to develop practical solutions for reducing FW. Through engagement with food businesses, policymakers, and consumers, BREADCRUMB will test interventions designed to improve consumer attitudes towards suboptimal foods and support businesses in adopting more sustainable practices. The results will be consolidated into policy and operational guidelines, ensuring that the project's findings contribute to long-term sustainability efforts and provide actionable recommendations for industry and policymakers.

Objectives

BREADCRUMB addresses food waste linked to food marketing standards by analyzing their impact on supply chains and exploring adjustments that promote sustainability. The project develops solutions to optimize standards, encourage circular economy approaches, and provide policy recommendations to align regulations with food waste reduction. Through stakeholder engagement and knowledge transfer, it ensures practical adoption of results.

Project details

Main funding source
 Horizon Europe (EU Research and Innovation Programme)

Type of Horizon project
 Multi-actor project - Advisory network

Project acronym
 BREADCRUMB

CORDIS Fact sheet

Project contribution to CAP specific objectives

- SO2. Increasing competitiveness: the role of productivity
- SO3. Farmer position in value chains

Project contribution to EU Strategies
 Improving management of natural resources used by agriculture, such as water, soil and air

Activities

BREADCRUMB will generate an inventory of both public and private food marketing standards and provide empirical evidence on FW levels associated with these regulations across five key food commodities: fruits & vegetables, meat, eggs, cereals, and fish. By employing advanced modeling techniques, the project will assess the underlying mechanisms that drive food waste, offering insights into how standards can be adjusted without compromising their original objectives.

The project also integrates behavioral and economic research to develop practical solutions for reducing FW. Through engagement with food businesses, policymakers, and consumers, BREADCRUMB will test interventions designed to improve consumer attitudes towards suboptimal foods and support businesses in adopting more sustainable practices. The results will be consolidated into policy and operational guidelines, ensuring that the project's findings contribute to long-term sustainability efforts and provide actionable recommendations for industry and policymakers.

Other comments
 Inventory of (private and public) food marketing standards

EUR 5 003 746.41 **EUR 5 003 746.41**
 Total budget EU contribution
 Total contributions including EU funding Any type of EU funding

Project keyword(s)

Supply chain, marketing and consumption Food security, safety, quality, processing and nutrition Circular economy, incl. waste, by-products and residues
 Climate change (incl. GHG reduction, adaptation and mitigation, and other air related issues) Competitiveness/business models

Resources

Links Audiovisual material

- BREADCRUMB project
- Food Navigator
- EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub
- Euronews

2 Practice Abstracts

- Reducing food waste related to food marketing standards across different commodities
- The Inventory of Food Marketing Standards

Figure 3. Submission of BREADCRUMB PAs on the EU CAP Network

4 SUBMITTED BREADCRUMB PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

This section presents the two practice abstracts developed as part of the BREADCRUMB project's first batch. Each abstract highlights a specific project outcome, offering practical insights and recommendations for stakeholders in the agri-food sector. PA1 (figure 4) depicts the outcomes of WP1, and PA2 (figure 5) of WP2.

4.1 BREADCRUMB Practice Abstract 1

Partner responsible for Practice Abstract 1: **VLTN**

Title: **The Inventory of Food Marketing Standards**

Summary:

The problem

Europe's food market follows many different rules set by both governments and private companies and organisations. The rules from the EU and national governments mostly focus on keeping food safe. Private rules add more things, like tracking where food comes from, caring for the environment, and treating animals well. For small suppliers, it can be hard to follow all these rules because they may not have enough money, time, or influence to keep up.

The Tool

To help people understand a complex set of standards, the BREADCRUMB project brought together specialists in food, agriculture, production, and distribution, and created an Inventory of Food Marketing Standards. This tool consolidates the main standards for fruits, vegetables, meat, eggs, cereals, and fish into a single document, making them easier to understand in relation to one another.

Benefits

- **Easier to find information:** The Inventory puts many different food rules into one document. This helps farmers and small businesses quickly find what they need to know, without having to look through lots of places.
- **Understanding market chances:** The Inventory shows which rules are already out there. This helps people see if a product that doesn't meet every rule can still be sold or used in other ways.
- **Helps with business choices:** The tool shows where a product might not meet some rules. This helps businesses decide what changes to make, which markets to focus on, and how to plan better.
- **Start for future improvements:** The Inventory is the first step in a bigger plan by the BREADCRUMB project. It will help future work that tries to reduce food waste and make food systems fairer and more sustainable.

Next Steps:

To download the Inventory of Food Marketing Standards, click on the [link](#).

2. The Inventory of Food Marketing Standards ↑

The problem

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Next Steps:

To download the Inventory of Food Marketing Standards, click on the link.

[Inventory of Food Marketing Standards](#) ↗

Geographical Location

📍 Région de Bruxelles-Capitale/ Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest

[🔗](#)

Figure 4. Practice Abstract 1: The Inventory of Food Marketing Standards

4.2 BREADCRUMB Practice Abstract 2

Partner responsible for Practice Abstract 2: **ILVO**

Title: **Reducing food waste related to food marketing standards across different commodities**

Summary:

Food marketing standards (FMS) are a set of rules and regulations designed to ensure that the market is supplied with standardized, high-quality agricultural products that meet consumer expectations in terms of appearance, quality, and safety. While these standards aim to guarantee product consistency and market transparency, they often impose rigid requirements - particularly concerning size, shape, colour, and

uniformity. This rigidity can create unintended consequences, especially for farmers, processors, and distributors working across diverse commodity groups.

In practice, the need to comply with multiple, sometimes overlapping, FMS results in financial and administrative burdens for farmers and processors and distributors. For perishable products such as fruits, vegetables, fish, meat, eggs, and cereals, the impact is evident. For example, misshapen fruits (e.g. small apple or discoloured spots) and vegetables (e.g. twisted, forked or multiple 'legs' carrot) may be discarded despite being safe and nutritious. In the meat and fish sectors, minor deviations from weight or appearance specifications can lead to the downgrading or rejection of entire batches. Eggs that do not meet shell uniformity or size standards, and cereal grains that fail to meet strict sorting criteria, are similarly subject to food waste.

To mitigate food waste across these key commodity groups and move toward a more sustainable certification framework, the following actions are recommended:

1. Promoting societal acceptance of imperfect produce, encouraging both consumers and retailers to embrace non-standard products.
2. Establishing robust networks that facilitate collaboration from producers to retailers

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2 Practice Abstracts

1. Reducing food waste related to food marketing standards across different commodities ▲

Food marketing standards (FMS) are a set of rules and regulations designed to ensure that the market is supplied with standardized, high-quality agricultural products that meet consumer expectations in terms of appearance, quality, and safety. While these standards aim to guarantee product consistency and market transparency, they often impose rigid requirements - particularly concerning size, shape, colour, and uniformity. This rigidity can create unintended consequences, especially for farmers, processors, and distributors working across diverse commodity groups.

In practice, the need to comply with multiple, sometimes overlapping, FMS results in financial and administrative burdens for farmers and processors and distributors. For perishable products such as fruits, vegetables, fish, meat, eggs, and cereals, the impact is evident. For example, misshapen fruits (e.g. small apple or discoloured spots) and vegetables (e.g. twisted, forked or multiple 'legs' carrot) may be discarded despite being safe and nutritious. In the meat and fish sectors, minor deviations from weight or appearance specifications can lead to the downgrading or rejection of entire batches. Eggs that do not meet shell uniformity or size standards, and cereal grains that fail to meet strict sorting criteria, are similarly subject to food waste.

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2. Establishing robust networks that facilitate collaboration from producers to retailers

[BREADCRUMB Food commodities](#)

Geographical Location

📍 Région de Bruxelles-Capitale/ Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest

Figure 5. Practice Abstract 2: Reducing food waste related to food marketing standards across different commodities

5 CONCLUSIONS

The first batch of BREADCRUMB Practice Abstracts presents valuable insights from WP1 and WP2 and practical tools to tackle food waste rooted in current food marketing standards.

PA1 offers a foundational resource—the Inventory of Food Marketing Standards—that consolidates fragmented information on both public and private FMS into a single, accessible document. This enables producers, particularly small- and medium-sized actors, to better understand and navigate the regulatory landscape, identify overlapping requirements, and pinpoint opportunities for innovation or exemption.

PA2 underscores the practical consequences of overly rigid FMS on different commodities, drawing attention to the types of quality criteria that often lead to unnecessary food loss. Through concrete examples, it illustrates how well-intentioned standards can result in economic, environmental, and social inefficiencies when they are not balanced with sustainability goals. Importantly, this second abstract moves beyond diagnosis and provides clear recommendations for action:

- ✓ Shifting consumer perceptions to normalize the purchase and use of non-standard produce,
- ✓ Encouraging retailers to revise purchasing requirements, and
- ✓ Fostering stronger networks across the supply chain to facilitate alternative uses and redistribution pathways for suboptimal food.

Both abstracts reflect the BREADCRUMB project's broader aim to make food systems more inclusive, efficient, and resilient. They also illustrate the project's commitment to ensuring that research outputs are translated into practical knowledge that can support real change on the ground—through both policy reform and industry practices.

These first PAs mark a meaningful step forward in BREADCRUMB's dissemination and exploitation strategy, setting the stage for continued engagement with practitioners and stakeholders in the next phase of the project.

The next PAs will focus on work done in WP3 and WP4 and will be presented in D5.8 (in M36).